

APPENDIX 2

DEPARTMENT SUB-UNIT-WISE PARTICIPANTS

S/N	Sub-Unit	Function	Number of Participants
1	Main Pharmacy, Phase I (Deals with NHIS)	Dispense NHIS prescriptions, oncology and antiretroviral to patients from antenatal clinic	3
2	Pharmacy Shop, Phase I	General outpatient drug services and non-NHIS prescriptions.	3
3	Central Drug Store, Phase I	Receiving and distribution of drugs to the various units and outstations.	3
4	Theatre Pharmacy, Phase II	Take custody and dispense drugs used in the theatre.	3
5	Basement Pharmacy, Phase II	Filling prescriptions and dispensing drugs of antidiabetics, antipsychotics, and antihypertensive.	3
6	Surgical/Medical Out-patient Pharmacy Phase II	Take custody and dispense drugs for medical outpatients.	3
7	Casualty Pharmacy	Attend to accident victims	3
8	Institute of Human Virology Pharmacy (IHVN) Phase III	Attend to HIV/Aids patients through counselling and dispensing of drugs	3
9	Ophthalmology Pharmacy Shop Phase III	This unit caters to the drug needs of the ophthalmology clinic and otorhinolaryngology patients.	3
10	Pediatric Pharmacy (UCHC Eleyele Centre)	Dispense drugs to patients	3
Total			30